

Towards the Green and Digital Transformation of the EU Energy Sector

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Welcome to the DIGITISE project!

Welcome to the first edition of the **DIGITISE Newsletter**, your gateway to the latest updates and insights from the project driving the digital energy transition.

In this inaugural issue, we feature the **launch press release**, highlighting the vision and objectives of DIGITISE. You'll also find exclusive **interviews with the Project Coordinator and Technical Coordinator**, offering a behind-the-scenes look at the project's foundation and technical roadmap.

To provide a comprehensive overview, we delve into **three key work packages**, showcasing how DIGITISE is advancing innovative energy solutions, fostering consumer empowerment, and building sustainable, data-driven systems.

We are also excited to announce the launch of the **E-ENERGY Cluster**, a collaboration of four Horizon Europe projects working together to drive digital innovation and enhance consumer participation in the energy transition.

Wishing you joyful holidays and a prosperous New Year filled with health, happiness, and success!

DIGITISE Team

Launch of the **DIGITISE** Project - Empowering Consumers in the Digital Energy Market

The **DIGITISE** project kicked off with a successful meeting in Athens, Greece, on June 5-6, 2024, marking the start of its mission to promote active engagement in digital energy markets and activities. DIGITISE is set to play a key role in the energy transition by enabling consumers and prosumers to take centre stage.

[Read the Press Release](#)

[Watch the reportage!](#)

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Eleni Tsironi

DIGITISE Coordinator
Electrical and Computer Engineer
UBITECH

DIGITISE: More Than Just Advancing Technology

Discover how the DIGITISE project is transforming the energy landscape in an exclusive interview with **Eleni Tsironi**, Project Coordinator. Learn how a diverse consortium is leveraging **AI, Digital Twins, Big Data Management**, and **DLT-enabled Marketplaces** to empower energy consumers and prosumers, enabling active participation in the digital energy market.

[Read the full interview](#)

Konstantinos Tsatsakis

DIGITISE Technical Coordinator
Energy Technology Lead
SUITE5

Leveraging AI, Digital Twins, and Collaboration for a Sustainable Tomorrow

Explore how the **DIGITISE project** is transforming the energy sector through technologies like **AI, Digital Twins, and Big Data** in an exclusive interview with **Konstantinos Tsatsakis**, Technical Coordinator from SUITE5. Delve into the technical progress, challenges, and innovative approaches that are driving DIGITISE’s mission to empower consumers and prosumers.

[Read the full interview](#)

The Role of Work Package 2 in Building the Framework for the DIGITISE Project

Work Package 2 (WP2) focuses on analysing requirements, designing a

Advancing Data Interoperability with DIGITISE's Data Model and Cross-domain Integration

Work Package 3 (WP3) is central to the DIGITISE project, focusing on developing an open-

Powering Real-World Change – Demonstration and Impact Assessment of DIGITISE Solutions

Work Package 6 (WP6) focuses on deploying and evaluating advanced

flexible architecture, and establishing a verification framework to enable interoperable, user-centered services that drive the energy transition within DIGITISE.

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standard data model and governance frameworks to ensure seamless, cross-domain data interoperability, enabling secure and efficient information sharing across sectors.

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energy solutions at pilot sites, ensuring their integration, optimisation, and impact on energy efficiency, cost savings, and consumer engagement.

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Launch of the E-ENERGY Cluster!

E-ENERGY

We are excited to announce the formation of “E-ENERGY,” a collaborative cluster uniting four Horizon Europe projects: [DIGITISE](#), [DECODIT](#), [ENERGENIUS](#), and [EU-DREAM](#). Together, these projects aim to harness the power of digital technologies to empower consumers and enhance their active participation in the energy transition.

Through this partnership, the E-ENERGY cluster seeks to democratise access to energy information, fostering inclusivity and engagement in the transition towards a more sustainable energy future. Stay tuned for updates on our progress and initiatives.

DIGITISE in a nutshell!

We invite you to watch this video about the DIGITISE project to discover how it is transforming the way consumers engage with digital energy systems and markets. See how DIGITISE is paving the way for a smarter, more inclusive digital energy future!

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